

Challenges in Teacher Preparation for Urdu Medium Schools: Perspectives of Pre-Service Teachers

Ambrin Khanam¹

Research Scholar, Email: ambrin288@gmail.com

Nisar Ahmad²

Research Scholar, Email: nahmad0803@gmail.com

Soumya Priyadarsani Panigrahi³

Research Scholar, Email: psoumyapanigrahi@gmail.com

Prof. Jasim Ahmad⁴

Professor of Education, Email: jahmad@jmi.ac.in

^{1,2,3,4} **Affiliation:** Dept. of Teacher Training and Non-Formal Education (IASE), Faculty of Education,
Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi-110025, India

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 15-05-2025

Published: 10-06-2025

Keywords:

*Urdu-medium pre-service
teaching, teacher training
programs, challenges,
resources*

ABSTRACT

Urdu-medium teaching in India is facing challenges that stem from various factors like linguistic translation, pedagogical restrictions and dearth of resources. This study intends to explore the experiences of pre-service teachers of Jamia Millia Islamia in Urdu-medium teacher training programs. The research follows a descriptive quantitative approach to describe the perception of pre-service teachers towards the challenges they have faced in their academic venture. Some of the challenges that are highlighted in the study are lack of adequate e-resources, conventional teaching methods, lack of Urdu-medium teacher educators. Unavailability of Urdu-medium schools in localities to do their teaching practice is also a constraint for Urdu-medium pre-

service teachers. This study underscores the need of systemic reforms like policies focusing on Urdu-medium teacher training programs along with a target to change the conditions of Urdu-medium schools by appointing well trained teachers. Improved resource allocations and production of e-resources in urdu-medium will empower the teachers to be confident in terminologies and jargons of their respective subject in Urdu. The findings of the study contribute to the understanding of key challenges of pre-service teaching and offers insight that can be used to enhance the efficacy of Urdu-medium teachers.

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15652720>

Introduction

Urdu has a historical significance as it has been widely spoken across the South Asian subcontinent. Being one of the vernacular languages in India, Urdu is rich in literary tradition. It has been central in establishing cultural identities of the people. Over centuries Urdu as a language has also influenced the medium of communication of various regions. Out of the 22 scheduled languages, Urdu is one of them and it also holds official status in several states of India. Its literary significance has also contributed to its role in disseminating knowledge. Historically, urdu has served as a medium of instruction in educational institutions all over the country. Urdu has been prevalent as a medium of instruction in schools because of its underlying linguistic abilities.

Strategies to promote Urdu language have been taken up by different states. To help the implementation of three-language formula, Uttar Pradesh government has recruited Urdu teachers to teach Urdu language at primary and secondary levels. Some of the states have Urdu as a medium from 1st to 10th class. Subjects like Science, Mathematics and Social Science are taught in Urdu. This requires Urdu medium teachers for teaching these subjects at all levels (Ahmed & Ansari, 2022).

It is necessary for Urdu-medium schools to recruit educators who are specifically trained in Urdu. For effective teaching in classrooms the teachers must possess proficient language skills along with pedagogical skills. To deliver subject content in Urdu-medium teachers require a hold on the linguistic framework of the language for intellectual development of students.

In order to promote the literary significance of Urdu language there are a few teacher training institutes which offer teacher training programs in Urdu-medium. But in implementing such programs there are several challenges that Urdu-medium pre-service teachers face. During their teacher practice and professional preparation they encounter a range of difficulties. These programmes need to be put in line with the curriculum framework of teacher education to facilitate academic achievements of Urdu-medium teachers (Ahmed & Ansari, 2022).

Teacher Training Institutes offering Urdu-Medium Teaching

Across India there are several institutions which offer specialized teacher training programs in Urdu-medium for aspiring teachers. Some of them are discussed below:

1. Academy of Professional Development of Urdu Medium Teachers (APDUMT), Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi: It was established to conduct orientation courses for teachers teaching various subjects like Science and Social Science, at all levels. It also works towards the development of professional skills of Urdu-medium teachers.
2. Urdu-Medium Government Primary Teachers' Training Institute, Nalikul, Hooghly, West Bengal: This institute operational since 1986, is a government institute which offers a Diploma in Elementary Education (D.El.Ed.) in Urdu-medium to train primary level teachers.
3. Maulana Azad National Urdu University (MANUU): It is a central university focused on promoting Urdu language. It offers Bachelors of Education (B.Ed.) and Masters of Education (M.Ed.) in Urdu-Medium. These programs prepare teachers teaching at all levels to be proficient in Urdu as a medium of instruction.
4. Dr. Abdul Haq Urdu University, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh: It is a state university established in 2016 to offer various teacher education programs to prepare teachers for Urdu-medium instruction.
5. Faculty of Education, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi: It is one of the early established faculty at the central university which offers courses like Bachelors of Education (B.Ed.) and Diploma in Elementary Education (D.El.Ed.) in Urdu-medium. It prepares teachers proficient in making lesson plans and disseminating the content in Urdu medium.

These institutions are crucial in equipping teachers with necessary skills and adequate knowledge base for effective teaching in Urdu-medium schools. They also contribute to preservation and promotion of the Urdu language in the educational realm of India.

Ignorance of Urdu-Medium Teaching in NEP-2020

Multilingualism in schools is given importance in the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. Multilingualism is suggested to be promoted in a way that local languages and mother tongue of students should be used as a medium of instruction. It also mentions recruiting teachers which can comfortably teach in regional languages. “Special attention will be given to employing local teachers or those with familiarity with local languages” (Para 2.3, Page 9).

Urdu being one of the vernacular languages in the pre-independence era does not find its mention in the NEP-2020. Although, the NEP-2020 does mention other classical languages having rich literature on which further developments will be done. “In addition to Sanskrit, other classical languages and literatures of India, including Tamil, Telugu, Kannada, Malayalam, Odia, Pali, Persian, and Prakrit, will also be widely available in schools as options for students, possibly as online modules, through experiential and innovative approaches, to ensure that these languages and literature stay alive and vibrant. Similar efforts will be made for all Indian languages having rich oral and written literatures, cultural traditions, and knowledge” (para 4.18, page13).

Urdu is not restricted to a particular region in India, albeit it is spoken by people spread across the country. The states in Northern India, West Bengal and Deccan have a significant number of people who speak Urdu (Shaban, 2015).

This portrays that Urdu is a language popular among a majority of population across the country. The NEP-2020 highlights the significance of all the languages listed in the Eighth Schedule of the Indian Constitution, which includes Urdu. An explicit mention of Urdu language or promotion of its literature has been mentioned in the policy. Focus on Urdu-medium teaching is lacking in the education policy of a country which already has a number of schools and institutions having Urdu as a medium of instruction. The absence of Urdu-medium education also leaves a loophole for the schools and institutions already having Urdu as a medium of instruction to implement the policy.

Jammu and Kashmir, Telangana, Bihar, Jharkhand, West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, NCT of Delhi and Andhra Pradesh have Urdu as their official language. It is also spoken as a mother tongue across these regions. Hence, Urdu medium schools in these regions also function, where a large number of children

study. Urdu is also adopted as a medium of instruction in these regions which have government, government-aided and private Urdu medium schools (Ansari, 2022).

Hence, a direct mention of the Urdu as medium of instruction in schools as a mother tongue would have helped in the implementation of the policy all over the country. It would have helped the stakeholders in promoting the literary significance of Urdu in teaching. Moreover, a focus on Urdu-medium teacher training would have also helped the pre-service teachers in implementing their pedagogical skills along in the literary realm.

Research Question

What are the key challenges faced by Urdu-medium pre-service teachers?

Objectives of the Study

- To study the key challenges faced by Urdu-medium pre-service teachers.
- To study the challenges in accessing the resources in Urdu medium.

Methodology

Population of the Study

The population of the study consists of all the Urdu-Medium pre-service teachers enrolled in teacher training courses offered by universities situated in Delhi.

Sample of the Study

The sample of the study consists of Urdu-medium pre-service teachers of Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi. A random sampling technique was used to collect the data.

Tools for Data Collection

A self prepared questionnaire was used to collect data from Urdu-medium pre-service teachers. The questionnaire was divided in two sections: first section consisted of demographic information and the next section had 20 statements related to the challenges in Urdu-medium teacher training courses. The questionnaire used a 5 point likert scale; it ranged from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

Procedure of Data Collection

The questionnaire was converted to a Google form and the link was shared to Urdu-medium pre-service teachers of Jamia Millia Islamia via respective class groups. A total of 50 responses were received from student enrolled in Diploma in Elementary Education (D.El.Ed.) and Bachelors of Education (B.Ed.).

Analysis of the Data

At the Department of Teacher Training and Non-Formal Education, Faculty of Education, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi, the two year D.El.Ed. course is conducted in Urdu and Hindi medium and the 2 year B.Ed. course is conducted in Urdu, Hindi and English medium. This study was conducted to analyse the difficulties faced by the students enrolled in Urdu-medium of these courses. The sample of the study consisted of students enrolled in Urdu-medium of respective courses from both first and second year. In this study they are referred as Urdu-medium pre-service teachers.

Results of the Study

In the self prepared questionnaire the Urdu-medium pre-service teachers were asked about their highest academic qualification, the course they are currently enrolled in and their perception regarding the Urdu-medium teacher training they are receiving in the currently enrolled course along with their future prospects.

Demographic Information

For the study the data was collected from students enrolled in D.El.Ed. and B.Ed. From the responses received 68% (34) participants were enrolled in D.El.Ed. and 32% (16) participants were enrolled in B.Ed. Both the teacher training programs represented in this study are conducted in Urdu-Medium at Jamia Millia Islamia. A representation of participants from both the courses indicates the challenges encountered in Urdu-medium teacher training courses at diploma level and at bachelors level.

Figure 1: Course enrolled

Figure 2 shows that 42% of the participants have completed their Senior Secondary School, and 40% have done a Bachelors degree whereas 18% of them have completed their Masters degree.

Figure 2: Highest academic qualification of the participants

For the two objectives of the study, the data obtained on the 5-point likert scale was tabulated using Microsoft Excel for analysis. The frequency and percentage was calculated for each item in the questionnaire. The objective wise analysis of the data is depicted in the form of tables. The tables depict the frequency and percentage distribution of responses showing levels of agreement and disagreement on the 5-point likert scale.

Analysis of Objective 1- To study the key challenges faced by Urdu-medium pre-service teachers

Table 1: Key challenges of faced by Urdu-medium pre-service teachers

S.No.	Statements	Strongly Agree سختی سے اتفاق	Agree اتفاق	Neutral غیر جانبدار	Disagree اختلاف	Strongly Disagree سختی سے اختلاف

1.	There is a shortage of Urdu-medium schools for teaching practice during pre-service teacher training. قبل از ملازمت اردو میڈیم اسکولوں کی تدریسی مشقوں کے لیے کمی ہے۔	20 (40%)	23 (46%)	5 (10%)	2 (4%)	(0%)
2.	Urdu-medium schools are easily available for employment after completing a teaching degree. تدریسی ڈگری مکمل کرنے کے بعد ملازمت کے لیے اردو میڈیم اسکول آسانی سے دستیاب ہیں۔	4 (8%)	8 (16%)	14 (28%)	17 (34%)	7 (14%)
3.	Teacher educators who are only from Urdu backgrounds are teaching us during our course. ہمارے کورس کے دوران صرف اردو پس منظر کے اساتذہ ہمیں پڑھا رہے ہیں۔	6 (12%)	8 (16%)	7 (14%)	17 (34%)	12 (24%)
4.	Traditional teaching methods like dictation and textbook-based learning predominate in Urdu-medium programs. اردو میڈیم پروگراموں میں روایتی تدریسی طریقے، جیسے املا اور نصابی کتابوں پر مبنی تعلیم، غالب ہیں۔	9 (18%)	19 (38%)	10 (20%)	8 (16%)	4 (8%)
5.	There are many difficulties in translating technical and scientific terms into Urdu. تکنیکی اور سائنسی اصطلاحات کو اردو میں ترجمہ کرنے میں	19 (38%)	19 (38%)	7 (14%)	3 (6%)	2 (4%)
6.	There is a lack of focus on Urdu-	20	14	10	5	1

	medium pre-service teacher education in government policies. سرکاری پالیسیوں میں اردو میڈیم قبل از ملازمت استاد کی تعلیم پر توجہ کی کمی ہے۔	(40%)	(28%)	(20%)	(10%)	(2%)
7.	Urdu-medium teachers are equally preferred as English-medium teachers in schools. اردو میڈیم اساتذہ کو اسکولوں میں انگریزی میڈیم اساتذہ کے برابر ترجیح دی جاتی ہے۔	6 (12%)	7 (14%)	9 (18%)	13 (26%)	15 (30%)
8.	The unavailability of national level tests such as CTET, CUET-PG, NET in Urdu medium restricts higher education opportunities for Urdu-medium pre-service teachers. قومی سطح کے امتحانات جیسے سی ٹی ای ٹی، سی یو ای ٹی پی جی، اور این ای ٹی کا اردو میڈیم میں نہ ہونا اردو میڈیم قبل از ملازمت اساتذہ کے لیے اعلیٰ تعلیم کے مواقع محدود کرتا ہے۔	22 (44%)z	14 (28%)	9 (18%)	5 (10%)	(0%)
9.	In India, there is a lack of master's programs in Education in Urdu medium. ہندوستان میں اردو میڈیم میں تعلیم کے ماسٹرز پروگراموں کی کمی	16 (32%)	20 (40%)	8 (16%)	6 (12%)	(0%)
10.	It is difficult for Urdu-medium pre-service teachers to attempt teacher eligibility tests like CTET or State TET. اردو میڈیم قبل از ملازم	7 (14%)	17 (34%)	11 (22%)	11 (22%)	4 (8%)

The above table depicts the perception of Urdu-medium pre-service teachers about the common challenges they have faced during their course. According to the analysis, 46% of the participants agree and 40% of them strongly agree to the statement that Urdu-medium schools are not readily available for teaching practice. Whereas 10% of them are neutral about this. This shows that the participants may have faced challenges in finding schools for their teaching practice which conduct classes in Urdu-medium. While talking of the employment, 34% of the participants disagree to the statement that Urdu-medium schools are readily available for them. When asked if the English medium teachers are equally preferred as Urdu medium teachers the more than 50% participants disagree or strongly disagree.

The participants were also given statements about their experience during the course. More than 50% of the participants disagree or strongly disagree that the teacher educators have an Urdu medium background. Most of the participants are inclined towards agreeing to the statement that Urdu-medium teaching involves more traditional ways of learning, while 20% of them are neutral about this. The translation of scientific and technical terms in Urdu can be challenge sometimes; majority of the participants agree or strongly agree to this. While 10% disagree to any difficulty faced during translation of these terms.

The future prospects of the teacher training programs were also discussed in the questionnaire. More than 50% of the participants agree or strongly agree that the unavailability of national level exams like CTET, CUET-PG, and NET restricts their opportunities in higher education. While 18% of them are neutral about this. Nearly 50% of the participants also find it difficult to attempt exams like CTET and state TET; while 14% of them are neutral about this and the rest of them do not find difficulty in attempting these exams. When asked about the focus of Urdu medium teaching in government policies more than 50% of the participants agree that the policies lack on formulating recommendations for Urdu medium teaching. A majority of the participants (72%) participants either agree or strongly agree that there is difficulty in finding Urdu-medium Masters program in Education like M.Ed. or M.A. Education, while 16% of them are neutral and 12% disagree to this.

Analysis of Objective 2: To study the challenges in accessing the resources in Urdu medium

Table 2: The challenges in accessing the resources in Urdu medium

S. No.	Statement	Strongly Agree سختی سے اتفاق	Agree اتفاق	Neutral غیر جانبدار	Disagree اختلاف	Strongly Disagree سختی سے اختلاف
1.	My university library has sufficient books and reference materials in the Urdu language. میری یونیورسٹی کی لائبریری میں اردو زبان میں کافی کتابیں اور حوالہ جاتی مواد موجود	13 (26%)	16 (32%)	6 (12%)	11 (22%)	4 (8%)
2.	The remote library of my university has adequate resources for Urdu-medium pre-service teachers. میری یونیورسٹی کی ریموٹ لائبریری میں اردو میڈیم قبل از ملازمت اساتذہ کے لیے کافی وسائل موجود	9 (18%)	20 (40%)	8 (16%)	9 (18%)	4 (8%)
3.	The available learning resources in Urdu are enough to cover pre-service teacher's academic requirements. اردو میں دستیاب تعلیمی وسائل قبل از ملازمت اساتذہ کی تعلیمی ضروریات کو پورا کرنے کے لیے کافی	3 (6%)	10 (20%)	16 (32%)	14 (28%)	7 (14%)

4.	I can easily find Urdu study materials over the internet. میں انٹرنیٹ پر اردو مطالعہ کے مواد آسانی سے تلاش کر سکتا	4 (8%)	12 (24%)	7 (14%)	12 (24%)	15 (30%)
5.	The availability of study materials in the Urdu medium is the same as the English medium. اردو میڈیم میں مطالعہ کے مواد کی دستیابی انگریزی میڈیم کے برابر	4 (8%)	12 (24%)	7 (14%)	12 (24%)	17 (34%)
6.	I can easily access research papers and journals in Urdu medium for my assignments. میں اپنے اسائنمنٹس کے لیے اردو میڈیم میں تحقیقی مقالے اور جرنلز آسانی سے حاصل کر سکتا	5 (10%)	5 (10%)	13 (26%)	16 (32%)	11 (22%)
7.	There are various educational websites and apps available in the Urdu medium. اردو میڈیم میں کئی تعلیمی ویب سائٹس اور ایپس دستیاب	4 (8%)	9 (18%)	12 (24%)	16 (32%)	9 (18%)

8.	Teachers are well-trained to deliver content effectively in the Urdu medium. اساتذہ اردو میڈیم میں مواد کو مؤثر طریقے سے پیش کرنے کی اچھی تربیت یافتہ	8 (16%)	20 (40%)	8 (16%)	10 (20%)	4 (8%)
9.	Teachers offer study materials in Urdu to support student learning. اساتذہ طلبہ کے سیکھنے میں مدد کے لیے اردو میں مطالعہ کا مواد فراہم کرتے	5 (10%)	18 (36%)	14 (28%)	9 (18%)	4 (8%)
10.	I feel like there is a need to add more study materials for Urdu-medium pre-service teachers. مجھے لگتا ہے کہ اردو میڈیم قبل از ملازمت اساتذہ کے لیے مزید مطالعہ کے مواد شامل کر کے کی ضروری	28 (56%)	14 (28%)	4 (8%)	3 (6%)	1 (2%)

The above table depicts the perception of Urdu-medium teachers regarding the availability and accessibility of the resources in Urdu-medium. The availability of books and resource materials in Urdu in the University library is satisfactory as 58% of the participants agree or strongly agree to this statement. While the availability of Urdu medium resources in remote library is also satisfactory as 58% of the participants either agree or strongly agree to it. The responses are dispersed when asked if these resources available in the library are enough to fulfil their academic requirement in the currently enrolled course. 32% of the participants are neutral about this while 28% disagree and 14% strongly disagree. This depicts that majority of the participants feel that the resources are not adequate to fulfil their academic requirements. There is no proper availability of Urdu study material over the internet as

depicted by the disagreement of 54% of the participants. While 58% of the participants also disagree to the statement that the resources in Urdu are as readily available as in English. A majority of participants also face difficulty in finding research articles and journals in Urdu when preparing their assignments; while 26% of them are neutral about this. When talking about the websites and apps available in Urdu the responses of participants are slightly inclined towards disagreement. More than 50% of the participants agree that the teachers are efficiently trained to teach in Urdu-medium. Near to 50% of the participants agree or strongly agree that their teachers provide content in Urdu-medium for their respective courses to support student learning; while 28% of them are neutral about this. When inquired about addition of more relevant Urdu-medium resources, 84% of the participants either agree or strongly agree. This depicts that they need more support in learning through Urdu-medium resources.

Discussion

The study is focused on the Urdu-medium pre-service teachers of Jamia Millia Islamia. It analyses their challenges during and after the teacher training course in Urdu-medium. The study was based on 34 D.El.Ed. students and 16 B.Ed. students who are pursuing the respective course in Urdu-medium. The objectives of the study were to analyse the key challenges faced by the Urdu-medium pre-service teachers and to assess their perception regarding availability and accessibility of resources in Urdu.

The findings reflect that there is a lack of Urdu-medium schools for students to do their teaching practice and for employment after attending the teacher training courses. Patel and Ansari (2022) also argue that there is a scarcity of Urdu-medium schools near universities so the pre-service Urdu-medium teachers are compelled to do their teaching practice in non Urdu-medium schools. Since not all states publish their subject textbooks in Urdu the pre-service teachers lack a primary resource i.e., textbooks. This as a result makes it difficult for them to prepare the lesson plans, teaching aids and class tests in Urdu.

One of the aspects that was reflected in the findings was that the participants believe that English medium teachers are preferred over Urdu medium teachers for employment in schools. While they also experienced that Urdu-medium teaching involves more traditional ways of learning and that there is lack of teacher educators from Urdu-medium background. The findings of the study also highlight that translating some scientific terms and jargons involved in teaching of school subjects can also be challenging. Ansari, A. (2022) suggests that students find it difficult in translating the terminologies used in Mathematics, Science and Social Science. The findings suggest that the Urdu-medium pre-

service teachers are confident in attempting national level exams due to unavailability of preferred medium and recession of study materials for such exams in Urdu-medium.

The findings of the second objective reflects that there is dearth of resources and study materials in Urdu-medium. While there is an availability of resources and books in the university library and the remote library, the findings also reflect that pre-service teachers struggled to locate e-resources in Urdu. Moreover, the findings indicate that pre-service teachers recognized the scarcity of resources in the Urdu language compared to those in English. This finding aligns with Ansari, A. (2022), as he discusses non-availability of materials and a dearth of quality books in Urdu medium. They also noted the difficulty of accessing research papers and journals in Urdu for their assignments. The findings further clarify the lack of educational sites and applications available in the Urdu language. The pre-service teachers are satisfied with the teacher preparedness in the course, they believe that the educators are well-trained and capable of providing students with study materials in Urdu. Even if they are satisfied with the educators in their course, there is a need of teacher educators who are particularly from Urdu background. They are well aware of the terminologies and will be able to uplift the conditions of Urdu-medium teachers in current scenario. Patel and Ansari (2022) highlight that there is a need to do research in Urdu-medium teacher training programs. The background of pre-service teachers and teacher educators should align in order to pursue an effective teacher training course. Well trained Urdu-medium teacher educators will be able to provide valuable, consistent and relevant academic inputs to the future teachers. The findings of the current study also highlight that there is a necessity of adding more relevant study well-trained and capable of providing students with study materials in Urdu. Ansari, A. (2022) also highlights the scarcity of qualified Urdu-medium teachers in schools.

Conclusion

Urdu has a rich literary culture and it has been widely spoken language in the country. Its literary significance has provided uniqueness to India's history. The country's history is a witness of the diaspora of Urdu as a culture and as a language. But, the language with such literary significance is becoming history; it is diminishing from the education system of the country. The convenient omission of Urdu from the NEP-2020 is a proof of that the language might be left behind if proper work is not done to promote it in schools as language or as a medium of instruction. The current study revolves around the key challenges that Urdu-medium pre-service teachers face in their teacher training courses. These challenges are related to lack of resources in Urdu-medium and absence of fulfilling e-resources

for their academic venture. Moreover, the absence of Urdu medium in the national level eligibility exams for teacher restricts the opportunities of pre-service teachers. Academy of Professional Development of Urdu Medium Teachers, JMI, Urdu-Medium Government Primary Teachers' Training Institute, West Bengal, Maulana Azad National Urdu University, Dr. Abdul Haq Urdu University and Faculty of Education, JMI, are some of the institutions in the country that are working towards Urdu-medium education in the country. India being a diverse country, deserves more such institutions which concentrate on the development of resources in Urdu-medium for students and also for future educators. Moreover, the education policies should also focus on developing a curriculum of teacher education that bridges the gap of e-resources for Urdu-medium teachers. To bring the Urdu-medium teachers to mainstream the dearth of study materials needs to be fulfilled. A focus on Urdu-medium teacher educators should also be included in the policies in order to impact future teachers in a way that they are confident about their employment after a teacher training course. The challenges in the study needs to be overcome with targeted interventions, enhanced teacher training programs and access to updated teaching-learning materials. The incorporation of new pedagogical techniques is needed in training the Urdu-medium teachers. The Urdu-medium teachers need to be backed up by updated e-resources in order to foster a more effective learning environment, which benefits both teachers and students.

References

- Ahmed, M. I., & Ansari, M. A. (2022). Training of teachers through distance mode: The experiences and challenges of training Urdu medium teachers. *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*, 10(94), 154–165. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8111843>
- Akbar, W., Burney, A. I., Aslam, A., & Mubin, M. (2014). Urdu medium intermediaries issues getting higher education in English medium institutions: Evidence from Pakistan. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(23), 37-38.
- Ali, N., & Kottacheruvu, N. (2022). Teaching creative writing skills to UG students of Urdu medium: Challenges and concerns. *Oriental Institute Journal*, 71(3), 153.
- Ansari, M. A. (2022). A study of the problems of teaching-learning in Urdu medium schools. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research*, 11(8[5]), Article 87. Sucharitha Publication. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8111843>

- Fareed, M., Ashraf, A., & Mushtaque, S. (2019). Medium of instruction in education: Perceptions of teachers and students from Pakistani school, college and university. *FWU Journal of Social Sciences*, 13(3), 134-143.
- Hussain, A., & Amanat, A. (2021). The Urdu and English medium divide in Punjab, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, 3(4), 616-621.
- Hussain, A., Amanat, A., & Tariq, M. U. (2021). Problem-based learning for Urdu medium language students to learn English language skills. *Pakistan Languages and Humanities Review*, 5(2), 47-57. [https://doi.org/10.47205/plhr.2021\(5-II-sep\)1.05](https://doi.org/10.47205/plhr.2021(5-II-sep)1.05)
- Javed, F. (2020). Adaptation challenges faced by Pakistani university entrants. *Student Success Journal*, 11(2), 41-43. <https://doi.org/10.5204/ssj.v11i3.1164>
- Khan, M. S. (2019). English language learning difficulties of students studying in Urdu medium schools. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research*, 8(4[3]), 32-34.
- Khurshid, M. A., & Hassan, R. (2014). Cognitive problems of Urdu-medium college students in learning English interrogative sentences. *Kashmir Journal of Language Research*, 17(2), 87-111.
- Ministry of Human Resource Development. (2020). *National education policy 2020*. Government of India. https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf
- Patel, M. A. I., & Ansari, M. A. (2022). Training of teachers through distance mode: The experiences and challenges of training Urdu medium teachers. *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*.
- Shaban, A. (2015). Urdu and Urdu Medium Schools in Maharashtra, Economic and political weekly, Vol. 50, Issue No. 29.